

An Augmented Reality Interface for Improving Task Performance in Close-Proximity Teleoperation

Pietro Balatti^{*,1,2}, Alessandro De Franco^{*,1,3}, Edoardo Lamon^{1,2}, Elena De Momi³, and Arash Ajoudani¹

Abstract—Although teleoperation applications are mainly associated with robots operating in remote, far-off sites, a large number of tasks in the industrial field requires teleoperation because of their potential danger, such as management of toxic waste, or human sourced contamination, such as in clean isolator systems. In some cases, the operator can be as close as possible to the isolated environment, to have a clear view of the task space for better situational awareness. To enhance the user awareness of the task and the environment in the absence of a direct contact, in this paper we present an augmented reality (AR) interface to provide the user with additional real-time information that can contribute to better task performances and safety. A proof-of-concept of the framework is presented for possible pharmaceutical operations, in which the user can select, through the AR interface, substances to be poured with teleoperation on a beaker placed on a scale.

I. INTRODUCTION

From the second half of the 20th century, the development of new teleoperation systems has been growing more and more, thanks to the giant steps made by technology, from more effective robotic manipulators to better communication means [1]. The application areas mainly include mining, underwater and space exploration, and surgery. Generally, these kind of applications are based on 2 or 3 dimensional video feedback to the operator, since the robotic manipulators are located in remote environments. However, extending human manipulation capabilities through teleoperation does not always concern far-off locations. In fact, there are applications based on a direct visual feedback, especially in the industrial field, that has been largely investigated for inspection and maintenance operations in hazardous environments [2], or for avoiding human sourced contamination, such as, for instance, teleoperated cleaning robots for radioactive environments [3]. Nevertheless, precise manipulation of hazardous or toxic substances, such as radioactive materials, usually requires the employment of shielded glove box isolators. In such cases, the operator directly insert his/her hands into the isolator gloves, to perform tasks inside the box without breaking containment. This kind of operation can lead to potential danger for the operator, being in close contact with the toxic substances. A teleoperation interface is potentially able to address these issues, provided that an accurate task feedback is given to the user.

* Contributed equally to this work.

¹HRI² Lab, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genoa, Italy.
 pietro.balatti@iit.it

²Dept. of Information Engineering, University of Pisa, Italy.

³Dept. of Electronics, Information and Bioengineering, Politecnico di Milano, Italy.

Fig. 1. The close-proximity teleoperation task is supported by an instant feedback shown through the AR interface.

To this end, in this paper we introduce a novel close-proximity teleoperation framework, through which the user awareness is enriched using an Augmented Reality (AR) interface. This choice was led by the effectiveness recently demonstrated by AR interfaces in Human-Robot Collaboration scenarios [4], [5]. Although the system is not limited to a specific application, as a proof of concept we demonstrate how teleoperation can be employed in place of glove box isolators, preventing the operator to be in close contact with potentially hazardous materials, or avoiding a human sourced contamination.

II. METHOD

Three main modules have been developed and integrated to build the software architecture illustrated in Fig. 2: 1) a robot controller that retrieves the robot status and commands the robot motions, 2) an AR communication handler necessary to receive user inputs from the AR device and to send the information to render the AR holograms, and 3) a Finite State Machine (FSM) in charge of coordinating all the components of the system.

The robot controller embeds a Cartesian impedance controller that is responsible of computing the robot joint torques needed to reach the target pose received by the FSM. This is achieved by means of a fifth-order polynomial trajectory planner as in [6]. This unit, reading the robot status, also regulates the switching between FSM states by triggering motion ending acknowledgments.

The AR communication handler communicates with the AR device and the FSM. It receives from the latter the task info that are translated in visual feedback shown on the AR device to augment the user awareness, and sends back the trigger given by the user input. This can be either given by voice

command or hand gesture acting upon the targeted element, based on the eye’s gaze. More details on the AR interface and communication are presented in [4].

Lastly, we design a Finite State Machine that coordinates the data coming from the aforementioned modules and the ones received by two other sensors, i.e. an IMU and a Force-Torque (FT) sensor. The IMU is mounted on the operator right hand and provides information about the hand orientation, needed for the robotic gripper teleoperation. The FT sensor is placed in the hostile environment with an empty beaker placed on top and acts as a scale to retrieve the weight of the substances that will be poured inside the container. The FSM initial and central state is given by the “Homing” state, where the system returns after performing each one of the three possible actions hereafter described.

a) *Task procedure*: the operator, by sending the vocal command “Procedure” can list the task process shown as an hologram that appears in front of him/her. This list can be moved in a more convenient position with the “tap” hand gesture, i.e. simulating a mouse click with the thumb and the forefinger, not to hinder the operator’s view.

b) *Substance information*: looking at the substance’s name located on the shelf, the operator can list the material information as holograms with the “tap” hand gesture.

c) *Substance selection and Teleoperation*: the operator can select the desired substance with a “tap” hand gesture, while pointing the gaze on the relative beaker. The robot then picks the substance and places it on top of the main beaker placed on the scale. With the vocal command “Start”, the operator enables the teleoperation phase and can pour the desired quantity of the substance by rotating his/her right hand. The weight of the main beaker content is shown through the AR interface. During teleoperation, the robot end-effector pose w.r.t. its base, T_b^{ee} , is computed as follows:

$$T_b^{ee} = T_{b_initial}^{ee} T_{hh_initial}^{hh} \quad (1)$$

where $T_{b_initial}^{ee}$ represents T_b^{ee} at the beginning of the phase and $T_{hh_initial}^{hh}$ the transformation of the current human hand w.r.t. to its initial value. To reduce the chances of human errors and increase the efficiency of the method, most of values of $T_{hh_initial}^{hh}$ are kept fixed, and the only variable that is subject to changes is the rotation on the axis in the direction of the human arm. Once the user pours the right substance quantity, he/she can disable the teleoperation with the voice input “Stop”, the robot places back the beaker on the shelf, and comes back to the “Homing” state, ready to start over another task.

III. EXPERIMENTS

To validate the proposed method, we carried out experiments using a Franka Emika Panda robotic arm, a Microsoft HoloLens AR device, an ATI Nano17 Force/Torque sensor and one Inertial Measurement Unit of the MVN Biomech suit (Xsens Tech). Copper Chloride and Molybdenum Sulfide have been used as substances. The experiments was performed by 5 subjects in two different scenarios, with and without the

Fig. 2. The system architecture is composed by three units that communicate with an AR device, a robotic manipulator, an IMU and a F/T sensor. The arrows within the Finite State Machine show the user inputs needed to trigger the different states.

AR interface feedback, measuring the time to complete the task and the accuracy. Without feedback the subjects could rely only on the graduate beakers, marked on the side with lines indicating the volume contained, while the AR interface enriched the situational awareness with holograms showing the amount of poured substance. The average time to pour the two substances without the AR feedback was 20.77s, while with the feedback 16.87s, i.e. 18.8% less. Without AR feedback, the experiments showed on average an error of 13.5%, while with the holograms feedback the subjects reached a much more accurate level of precision, resulting in a 2.2% error. A video of the experiment is available in the multimedia material.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed a novel framework for close-proximity teleoperation tasks, in which the operator situational awareness is improved with an AR interface. We carried out experiments with 5 subjects demonstrating that the task performances are improved in terms of both precision and time.

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